

The Exact Solution of Fitzhugh–Nagumo Equation by the Variational Iteration Method

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Abstract: In this study, the Variational Iteration Method (VIM) is applied to the Fitzhugh–Nagumo non-linear differential equations. Two case study problems of Fitzhugh–Nagumo are solved by using the VIM and the exact solutions are obtained. The results present capabilities and great potential of the VIM in solving the Fitzhugh–Nagumo equation as a non-linear differential equation.

Keywords: Fitzhugh–Nagumo equation, Variational Iteration Method, Nonlinear differential equations

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1. Introduction

Nonlinear differential equations are introduced to model behavior and effects of many phenomena in different fields of science and engineering by mathematical concepts. In order to solve the equations, Semi-analytical method as the Variational Iteration Method (VIM) is used. The VIM has no specific requirements for nonlinear operators, discretization, linearization, transformation or perturbation. The Variational Iteration Method (VIM) is a strong and efficient method which can be widely used to handle linear and nonlinear models due to flexibility of applications, convenience and accuracy of obtained results.

The Variational Iteration Method (VIM) was first pioneered by He [1]. Then, the VIM is applied by He [2], [3] in order to solve autonomous ordinary differential equation as well as delay differential equation. Also, new development and applications of the VIM to nonlinear wave equation, nonlinear fractional differential equations, nonlinear oscillations and nonlinear problems arising in various engineering applications is presented by He and Xh [4].

Nourazar et al. [5] obtained the exact solution of the Fitzhugh–Nagumo equation by using the homotopy perturbation method. In order to find exact solution of nonlinear differential equations, the homotopy perturbation method is applied by Nourazar et al. [6], [7]. A finite-difference scheme to approximate non-negative and bounded solutions of a FitzHugh–Nagumo equation is presented by Ruiz-Ramírez and Macías-Díaz [8]. Also, Arioli and Koch [9] presented existence and stability of traveling pulse solutions of the FitzHugh–Nagumo equation. Soori et al. [10], [11] presented application of the Variational Iteration Method and the Homotopy Perturbation Method to the fisher type equation. Moreover, Soori [12] presented Series Solution of Weakly-Singular Kernel Volterra Integro-Differential equations by the Combined Laplace-Adomian Method.

Application of the Variational Iteration Method for the Newell-Whitehead-Segel Equation is presented by Soori [13].

The Fitzhugh–Nagumo equation models the interaction of the effect of the diffusion term with the nonlinear effect of the reaction term. It is an important nonlinear reaction–diffusion equation which is applied to model the transmission of nerve impulses [14], [15]. It is also used in biology, the area of population genetics, transmission of heat mass transfer as well as circuit theory .The Fitzhugh–Nagumo equation is written as:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} - u(1 - u)(a - u) \quad (1.1)$$

Where a is arbitrary constant.

The first term on the right hand side, $\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}$, expresses the variations of $u(x, t)$ with spatial variable x at a specific time and the remaining terms on the right hand side, $u(1 - u)(a - u)$, takes into account the effect of the source term. In Eq. (1.1) $u(x, t)$ is a function of the spatial variable x and the temporal variable t , with $x \in R$ and $t \geq 0$.

In the present research work, the Variational Iteration Method (VIM) is applied in order to obtain the closed form solution of the non-linear Fitzhugh–Nagumo equation. The main aim of the study is to present trend of rapid convergence of the sequences constructed by the VIM toward the exact solution of the equation. So, two case study problems of non-linear Fitzhugh–Nagumo equations are solved by using the VIM and the exact solution is obtained.

The ideas of variational iteration method is presented in the section 2. Application of the variational iteration method to the exact solution of Fitzhugh–Nagumo equation is presented in the section 3.

2. The idea of variational iteration method

The idea of the variational iteration method is based on constructing a correction functional by a general Lagrange multiplier. The multiplier is chosen in such a way that its correction solution is improved with respect to the initial approximation or to the trial function. To illustrate the basic idea of the variational iteration method, consider the following nonlinear equation:

$$Lu(t) + Nu(t) = g(t), \quad (2.1)$$

Where L is a linear operator, N is a nonlinear operator, and $g(t)$ is a known analytic function. According to the variational iteration method, we can construct the following correction functional:

$$u_{n+1}(x, t) = u_n(x, t) + \int_0^t \lambda(\xi) (Lu_n(\xi) + N\tilde{u}_n(\xi) - g(t)) d\xi, \quad (2.2)$$

Where λ is a general Lagrange multiplier which can be identified optimally via variational theory and $\tilde{u}_n$ is considered as a restricted variation which means $\delta\tilde{u}_n = 0$.

$u_0(t)$ is an initial approximation with possible unknowns. We first determine the Lagrange multiplier λ that will be identified optimally via integration by parts. With λ determined, then several approximations $u_n(t)$, $n \geq 0$ follow immediately. Consequently, the exact solution may be obtained as:

$$u(t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n(t), \quad (2.3)$$

The correction functional of the Eq. (2.1) gives several approximations. Therefore, the exact solution can be obtained as the limit of resulting successive approximations.

3. The Fitzhugh–Nagumo equation

To illustrate the capability and reliability of the method, two cases of nonlinear diffusion equations are presented.

Case I: In this case we will examine the Fitzhugh–Nagumo equation for $a = 2$, equation is written as:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} - u(1 - u)(2 - u) \quad (3.1)$$

Subject to a constant initial condition:

$$u(x, 0) = \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 2e^{\sqrt{2}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1} \quad (3.2)$$

The correction functional for Eq. (3.1) is in the following form:

$$u_{n+1}(x, t) = u_n(x, t) + \int_0^t \lambda(\xi) \left(\frac{\partial u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + 2u_n(x, \xi) - 3u_n^2(x, \xi) + u_n^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi, \quad (3.3)$$

Where u_n is restricted variation $\delta u_n = 0$, λ is a Lagrange multiplier and u_0 is an initial approximation or trial function.

With the above correction functional stationary we have:

$$\delta u_{n+1}(x, t) = \delta u_n(x, t) + \delta \int_0^t \lambda(\xi) \left(\frac{\partial u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + 2u_n(x, \xi) - 3u_n^2(x, \xi) + u_n^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi,$$

$$\delta u_{n+1}(x, t) = \delta u_n(x, t) \delta \int_0^t \lambda(\xi) \left(\frac{\partial u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} \right) d\xi, \quad (3.4)$$

$$\delta u_{n+1}(x, t) = \delta u_n(x, t) (1 + \lambda(\xi)) - \delta \int_0^t \lambda'(\xi) u_n(x, \xi) d\xi,$$

By using the following stationary conditions:

$$\delta u_n : 1 + \lambda(\xi) = 0, \quad (3.5)$$

$$\delta u_n : \lambda'(\xi) = 0, \quad (3.6)$$

This gives the Lagrange multiplier $\lambda(\xi) = -1$, therefore the following iteration formula becomes as:

$$u_{n+1}(x, t) = u_n(x, t) - \int_0^t \left(\frac{\partial u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + 2u_n(x, \xi) - 3u_n^2(x, \xi) + u_n^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi, \quad (3.7)$$

We can select $u_0(x, y) = \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 2e^{\sqrt{2}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1}$, from the given condition.

Using this selection into the Eq. (3.7) the following successive approximation can be obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned} u_0(x, t) &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 2e^{\sqrt{2}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1}, \\ u_1(x, t) &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 2e^{\sqrt{2}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1} - \int_0^t \left(\frac{\partial u_0(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_0(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + 2u_0(x, \xi) - 3u_0^2(x, \xi) + u_0^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi \\ &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 2e^{\sqrt{2}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1} + \frac{3}{2} \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} (e^{\sqrt{2}x} - 1)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1 \right)^2} t, \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
u_2(x, t) &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 2e^{\sqrt{2}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1} + \frac{3}{2} \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}(e^{\sqrt{2}x} - 1)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1\right)^2} t \\
&\quad - \int_0^t \left(\frac{\partial u_1(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_1(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + 2u_1(x, \xi) - 3u_1^2(x, \xi) + u_1^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi \\
&= \frac{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 2e^{\sqrt{2}x}\right)}{6\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1\right)^2 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right) (-1 + e^{\sqrt{2}x})} \left(-2\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2 + 20e^{\sqrt{2}x} \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2\right. \\
&\quad \left.+ 26e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}(e^{\sqrt{2}x})^2 - 6e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 3\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^3 + 16e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 8(e^{\sqrt{2}x})^3 + 16(e^{\sqrt{2}x})^2\right) \\
&\quad + \frac{3}{2} \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}(e^{\sqrt{2}x} - 1)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1\right)^2} t + \frac{9}{8} \frac{(-1 + e^{\sqrt{2}x})e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - e^{\sqrt{2}x} - 1\right)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1\right)^3} t^2 \\
&\quad - \frac{9\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2 (-1 + e^{\sqrt{2}x})^3}{4\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1\right)^5} t^3 - \frac{27\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^3 (-1 + e^{\sqrt{2}x})^3}{32\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1\right)^6} t^4,
\end{aligned}$$

As a result, the series of the exact solution of the Eq. (3.1) can be constructed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
u_n(x, t) &= \frac{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 2e^{\sqrt{2}x}\right)}{6\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1\right)^2 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right) (-1 + e^{\sqrt{2}x})} \left(-2\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2 + 20e^{\sqrt{2}x} \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2 + 26e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}(e^{\sqrt{2}x})^2\right. \\
&\quad \left.- 6e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 3\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^3 + 16e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 8(e^{\sqrt{2}x})^3 + 16(e^{\sqrt{2}x})^2\right) + \frac{3}{2} \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}(e^{\sqrt{2}x} - 1)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1\right)^2} t \\
&\quad + \frac{9}{8} \frac{(-1 + e^{\sqrt{2}x})e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - e^{\sqrt{2}x} - 1\right)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1\right)^3} t^2 - \frac{9\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2 (-1 + e^{\sqrt{2}x})^3}{4\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1\right)^5} t^3 \\
&\quad - \frac{27\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^3 (-1 + e^{\sqrt{2}x})^3}{32\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1\right)^6} t^4 + \dots \tag{3.9}
\end{aligned}$$

Using the identity:

$$u(x, t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n(x, t), \tag{3.10}$$

We can write Eq. (3.9) in the closed form as:

$$v(x, t) = \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x - \frac{3}{2}t} + 2e^{\sqrt{2}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x - \frac{3}{2}t} + e^{\sqrt{2}x} + 1}, \quad (3.11)$$

This is the exact solution of the problem, Eq. (3.1).

Case II: In this case we will examine the Fitzhugh–Nagumo equation for $a = 3$, equation is written as:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} - u(1-u)(3-u), \quad (3.12)$$

Subject to initial condition:

$$u(x, 0) = \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 3e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1}, \quad (3.13)$$

The correction functional for Eq. (3.12) is in the following form:

$$u_{n+1}(x, t) = u_n(x, t) + \int_0^t \lambda(\xi) \left(\frac{\partial u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + 3u_n(x, \xi) - 4u_n^2(x, \xi) + u_n^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi, \quad (3.14)$$

Where u_n is restricted variation $\delta u_n = 0$, λ is a Lagrange multiplier and u_0 is an initial approximation or trial function.

With the above correction functional stationary we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta u_{n+1}(x, t) &= \delta u_n(x, t) + \delta \int_0^t \lambda(\xi) \left(\frac{\partial u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + 3u_n(x, \xi) - 4u_n^2(x, \xi) + u_n^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi, \\ \delta u_{n+1}(x, t) &= \delta u_n(x, t) \delta \int_0^t \lambda(\xi) \left(\frac{\partial u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} \right) d\xi, \end{aligned} \quad (3.15)$$

$$\delta u_{n+1}(x, t) = \delta u_n(x, t) (1 + \lambda(\xi)) - \delta \int_0^t \lambda'(\xi) u_n(x, \xi) d\xi,$$

By using the following stationary conditions:

$$\delta u_n : 1 + \lambda(\xi) = 0, \quad (3.16)$$

$$\delta u_n : \lambda'(\xi) = 0, \quad (3.17)$$

This gives the Lagrange multiplier $\lambda(\xi) = -1$, therefore the following iteration formula becomes as:

$$u_{n+1}(x, t) = u_n(x, t) - \int_0^t \left(\frac{\partial u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + 3u_n(x, \xi) - 4u_n^2(x, \xi) + u_n^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi, \quad (3.18)$$

We can select $u_0(x, y) = \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 3e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1}$, from the given condition.

Using this selection into the Eq. (3.18) the following successive approximation can be obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned}
u_0(x, t) &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 3e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1}, \\
u_1(x, t) &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 3e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1} - \int_0^t \left(\frac{\partial u_0(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_0(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + 3u_0(x, \xi) - 4u_0^2(x, \xi) + u_0^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi \\
&= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 3e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1} \\
&\quad + \frac{\left(16e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 5e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 9e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)}{2 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1 \right)^2} t, \tag{3.19}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
u_2(x, t) &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 3e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1} + \frac{\left(16e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 5e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 9e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)}{2 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1 \right)^2} t \\
&\quad - \int_0^t \left(\frac{\partial u_1(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_1(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + 3u_1(x, \xi) - 4u_1^2(x, \xi) + u_1^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi \\
&= \frac{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 3e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)}{6 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1 \right)^2 \left(16e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 5e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 9e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)} \left(181e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)^2 \right. \\
&\quad - 14 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)^2 + 216e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 30e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 255e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \left(e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)^2 + 54e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 198 \left(e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)^2 \\
&\quad \left. + 13 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)^3 + 63 \left(e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)^3 \right) + \frac{\left(16e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 5e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 9e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)}{2 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1 \right)^2} t \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{8 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1 \right)^3} \left(128e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)^2 - 25 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)^2 + 140e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right. \\
&\quad \left. - 128e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \left(e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)^2 + 25e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 27e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 27 \left(e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)^2 \right) t^2 \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{12 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1 \right)^5} \left(\left(16e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 5e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 9e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)^2 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 5e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 4 \right) \right) t^3 \\
&\quad - \frac{\left(16e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 5e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 9e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} \right)^3}{32 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1 \right)^6} t^4,
\end{aligned}$$

As a result, the series of the exact solution of the Eq. (3.12) can be constructed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
u_n(x, t) = & \frac{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 3e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)}{6\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1\right)^2} \left(16e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 5e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 9e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right) \left(181e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2 - 14\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2\right) \\
& + 216e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 30e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 255e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\left(e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2 + 54e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 198\left(e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2 + 13\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^3 \\
& + 63\left(e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^3 \Bigg) + \frac{\left(16e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 5e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 9e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)}{2\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1\right)^2} t \\
& + \frac{1}{8\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1\right)^3} \left(128e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2 - 25\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2 + 140e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right. \\
& \left. - 128e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\left(e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2 + 25e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 27e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 27\left(e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2\right) t^2 \\
& + \frac{1}{12\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1\right)^5} \left(\left(16e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 5e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 9e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^2 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 5e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 4\right)\right) t^3 \\
& - \frac{\left(16e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x}e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} - 5e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 9e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x}\right)^3}{32\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x} + 1\right)^6} t^4 + \dots \tag{3.20}
\end{aligned}$$

Using the identity:

$$u(x, t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n(x, t), \tag{3.21}$$

We can write Eq. (3.20) in the closed form as:

$$v(x, t) = \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x - \frac{5}{2}t} + 3e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x + \frac{3}{2}t}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x - \frac{5}{2}t} + e^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x + \frac{3}{2}t} + 1}, \tag{3.22}$$

This is the exact solution of the problem, Eq. (3.12).

4. Conclusion

In the present research work, the exact solution of the Fitzhugh–Nagumo nonlinear diffusion equation is obtained using the VIM. The validity and effectiveness of the VIM is shown by solving two non-homogenous non-linear differential equations. Convergence of sequences obtained by using the VIM towards the exact solutions indicates validity and great potential of the method as a powerful algorithm to solve the Fitzhugh–Nagumo equation. Moreover, it can be concluded that the VIM is a very efficient and powerful technique with acceptable accuracy in order to construct the exact solution of linear and nonlinear differential equations.

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